

Studies on the effects of cyclohexyl benzthiazylsulfenamide accelerated sulfur vulcanization of natural rubber : Thermochemistry and oxidative aging

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Typical cyclohexyl benzthiazylsulfenamide (CBS) and binary accelerated sulfur-cured natural rubber (NR) were prepared and subjected to aging at 100° in an air oven. Single accelerator gum specimen vulcanizates exhibited an initial stiffness behavior, while blend accelerator systems were found to soften. Tensile strength and strain-to-break values of all the vulcanizates were significantly reduced. Fractional strain-energy, TE(f), with aging time relationship suggested the heat stability criteria of the vulcanizates.

Aging of rubber has great significance because rubber vulcanizates undergoes considerable changes in their physical properties¹. Aging behavior of sulfur vulcanizates depends on many factors namely the type and degree of curing. Accordingly, free sulfur and combined sulfur present in the vulcanizate have marked influence upon aging properties. In case of combined sulfur, the types of combination (mono, di, poly, cyclic etc.) and their proportions are very important. Some other entities like carbon black, conventional antioxidants etc. also influence the aging properties. As all these entities have both specific and combinatorial effects, so the matter will be very difficult to understand if all the entities are present in the system.

Moreover, aging behavior depends on the process variations. Buist² mentioned shelf aging or natural oxidation, metallic poisoning, heat aging, light aging, flex cracking and atmospheric cracking. The fundamental reaction responsible for aging is almost same. It is the oxidation of rubber hydrocarbon by oxygen and ozone³. The oxidation reaction is 'triggered' or activated by different forces. The forces are different in nature and magnitude.

The purpose of this paper is to elucidate the oxidation characteristics of the vulcanizates which are sulfur cured and accelerated by the accelerator cyclohexyl benzthiazyl sulfenamide (CBS) and its blend with ultra accelerators like tetramethylthiuram disulfide (TMTD), zinc diethyl dithiocarbamate (ZDC). The vulcanizates are protected by the antioxidant *N*-isopropyl *N*-phenyl-*p*-phenylene diamine (IPPD) in each case. In the present investigation sample is aged at 100 ± 5° in an airoven for a couple of days. The aging performance of the vulcanizates will be assessed by the concept of fractional strain energy⁴, TE(f), which is

reasonably consistant with retained energy and also with respect to different aging period.

Results and discussion

The recipes of the experimented stocks are given in Table 1. The stocks are classified into several curing systems. System I is CBS accelerator sulfur (A, B, C and D). These stocks have different sulfur-accelerator weight ratios. The structures of CBS accelerated sulfur vulcanizates have been studied by Moore and Trego⁵. At optimum crosslinking the structures are : polysulfide about 70%, monosulfide about 15% and disulfide about 15%. Sulfur generally combines in the form of crosslinks but part remains as cyclic monosulfide (major amount). Thermal aging resistance decreases with increase in proportion of di and polysulfide. The system I vulcanizates are different from each other in respect to the amounts of mono, di and polysulfide etc. produced due to different sulfur accelerator ratios used in the

Table 1. Basic recipe of the mixes (parts by weight)

Ingredients	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Natural rubber (RMAI)	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Stearic acid	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
IPPD*	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sulfur	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
CBS	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	0.6	0.8	1.0	0.6	0.8
TMTD	-	-	-	-	0.4	0.4	0.4	-	-
ZDC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.4	0.4

*IPPD (*N*-isopropyl-*N*-phenyl-*p*-phenylenediamine)

recipes lower ratio of sulfur-accelerator gives lower amount of polysulfide and disulfide crosslinks. Cyclic sulfur is also decreased. These structure variations may affect aging behavior to various degrees. System II is CBS-TMTD accelerated sulfur system. TMTD is an ultra accelerator and has capability to supply sulfur. Therefore it increases mono sulfide crosslink percentage of the vulcanizate. The scavenging action of sulfonamide is known. It reacts rapidly with hydrogen sulfide and thiols which is a delayed action chemical in vulcanization⁶. So the structural feature of the networks changes with TMTD used in combination with CBS in different weight proportions resulting in different aging behavior of the vulcanizates. System III is CBS-ZDC accelerated sulfur. Here the accelerator ZDC is an ultra accelerator and has been established that strongly dissociates into zinc thiolate complex and sulfur⁷.

The three important systems are widely used in different product applications. However, the proper choice of the system for a particular heat resistance application is very important depending on the optimization of aging properties of rubber.

The stress-strain behavior of the gum natural rubber vulcanizates are shown in Fig. 1 (system I) and in Fig. 2 (system II and III). The results of aging vs the stress-strain relationship of the vulcanizates are shown in Fig. 3 (24 hours of aging), Fig. 4 (48 hours of aging) and Fig. 5 (72 hours of aging) respectively.

In the elastic region of force-deformation behavior, the statistical theory⁸ predicts that tension stress, σ , is related to extension as

$$\sigma = G (\lambda - 1/\lambda^2)$$

where λ is the extension ratio. At a low elongation strain (ϵ), it reduces to

$$\sigma = 3G \epsilon = E_0 \epsilon$$

where E_0 is the modulus indicating the stiffness of the materials. For gum vulcanizates stress rises well with strain at low strain region only. Therefore low strain modulus is required for analyzing oxidative aging behavior. The results of aging on the stress-strain behavior of the vulcanizates are shown in Figs. 6 to 9 for system I, in Figs. 10 to 12 for system II and in Figs. 13 and 14 for system III. The values of relative 50% modulus ($R\sigma_{50}$) are plotted against time of aging in Fig. 15. The system I (gum vulcanizates) shows initially hardening (increase in modulus) on aging before degradation occurs. Only the vulcanizate 'D' appears exceptional. The vulcanizates of system II and III are observed soften with aging.

Fig. 1. Plots of stress vs strain of CBS accelerated sulfur cured NR vulcanizates (system I).

Fig. 2. Plots of stress vs strain of CBS-TMTD/ZDC accelerated sulfur cured NR vulcanizates (system II and III).

Fig. 3. Plots of stress vs strain of the vulcanizates after 24 hours of aging.

The sulfur vulcanizates having high sulfur-accelerator weight ratios are very prone to network (crosslink) scission during oxidative aging. Some of the scission products give

Fig. 4. Plots of stress vs strain of the vulcanizates after 48 hours of aging.

Fig. 5. Plots of stress vs strain of the vulcanizates after 72 hours of aging.

Fig. 6. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'A' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 7. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'B' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 8. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'C' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 9. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'D' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 10. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'E' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 13. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'H' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 11. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'F' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 14. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'I' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 12. Plots of stress vs low strain of 'G' after various aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 15. Plots of relative 50% modulus vs aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

rise to new crosslink⁹. This may be the probable cause of initial rise of stiffness for system I vulcanizates. The new crosslinks are related with the oxidative reactions of sulfur species (cyclic sulfides) in the network.

The loss of physical properties as observed (lower $R\sigma_{50}$) is due to the molecular degradation by scission of rubber chains. The fall in molecular weight of the rubber chain is the probable cause of variation of stress-strain behavior. When the specimens aged for 3 days, system II and III vulcanizates showed nearly identical resist deformation curve. The extended softening stage (a little change of $R\sigma_{50}$ with time) is prominent in both the two systems.

Relative tensile strength ($R\sigma_b$) and relative strain-to-break ($R\epsilon_b$) of the three systems are given in Figs. 16 and 17. The plots of the vulcanizates show some common features. During the initial aging period the $R\sigma_b$ and $R\epsilon_b$ values of all the vulcanizates decrease followed by an extended pattern (almost parallel to the time axis) over the range of aging. The results are consistent to the work¹⁰ using TBBS (*N-t*-butyl benzothiazole-2-sulfenamide) accelerated sulfur vulcanizates of natural rubber^{10,11}.

Fig. 16. Plots of relative tensile strength vs aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 17. Plots of relative strain to break vs aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

Fig. 18. Plots of TE(f) of the vulcanizates with aging times (24 h, 48 h and 72 h).

However the vulcanizates of all the systems show significant reduction in ultimate physical properties (Table 2) which indicate poor heat resistance property. Oxidized skin and crack formation may be the possible explanation¹⁰. It

Table 2. Ultimate strength properties of the vulcanizates before and after aging in kg cm^{-2}

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
Unaged (T.S.)	33.48	34.00	36.75	34.41	30.00	33.33	55.63	67.62	55.23
Aged (T.S.) _{24h}	6.06	11.60	12.95	4.33	13.41	4.78	5.80	3.82	3.70
Aged (T.S.) _{48h}	3.96	7.00	9.00	2.60	5.80	3.50	4.50	2.70	3.00
Aged (T.S.) _{72h}	1.92	4.00	6.40	1.60	4.00	2.40	3.00	1.60	2.20
Unaged (E.B.)	12.12	14.80	9.27	5.50	7.50	7.00	6.30	7.78	7.15
Aged (E.B.) _{24h}	3.14	1.77	3.00	2.71	1.56	2.80	1.40	1.74	2.50
Aged (E.B.) _{48h}	2.00	1.29	2.37	1.87	1.37	1.80	1.12	1.27	1.67
Aged (E.B.) _{72h}	1.37	0.75	2.10	1.57	1.00	1.20	0.80	0.92	0.87

* h (hours of aging).

creates a strength reducing stress-concentration.

The plots of TE(f) versus aging period are shown in Fig. 18. The results indicate the heat stability of the vulcanizates. The result shows maximum heat stability in 'C' and minimum in 'H'.

During aging, network chain formation and scission take place simultaneously. These processes depend on the sulfur-accelerator ratio, types of the accelerator used, types elastomer used etc. Network chain formation depends on residual curatives, rearrangement of crosslink sulfur. Chain scission is responsible for the amount of poly, di and mono sulfidic crosslink present. Aging causes due to the decrease in polysulfide amount and increases in mono sulfide. This is the cause of reduction of strength. The present experiment (reduction of σ_b and ϵ_b due to aging) on various types of sulfur vulcanizates clearly confirmed the facts.

Finally it is inferred that the aging behavior of CBS accelerated sulfur vulcanizates of natural rubber is controlled by the formation of the network structures of the vulcanizates.

Experimental

CBS and binary accelerated-sulfur vulcanized NR compositions are given in Table 1. All compounds were prepared on a laboratory size two-roll mill (30 cm × 15 cm) at a friction ratio of 1 : 1.25 according to ASTM D3185-88. Cure characterization was carried out with a Monsanto rheometer (R100) with a micro-die and a 3° arc of oscillation at a temperature 140° according to ASTM D2084-88. The vulcanization of test specimen (sheet) was carried out in 46 cm × 46 cm platens using an electrically heated press maintained at 140° and 45 kg/cm² pressure. Dumbbell specimens

were cut from the vulcanized sheets and tested according to ASTM D412-87 in an Instron4301 at a pulling rate of 50 cm/min at room temperature 30°. For each aging, three specimens were tested and the results averaged. Aging was carried out in an air oven at 100°.

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